

Taxonomy of a gamified lesson path for STEM education: The Beaconing approach

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Abstract

21st Century learning focuses on different skills and expertise that learners should develop for a successful life and career, and these are usually organised into four main categories: ways of thinking (e.g. creativity, innovation, critical thinking, problem-solving); ways of working (e.g. communication and collaboration); tools for working (e.g. digital literacy) and living in the world (e.g. citizenship, social responsibility, awareness). Learning should be reshaped to better match these requirements and prepare learners for open societies where learning will be lifelong and based on critical-thinking, cultural awareness, flexibility and adaption to changes. This paper introduces a new approach developed under the scope of the Beaconing project, which aims to contextualise the teaching and learning process, connecting it with problem-based mechanics within STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics). The aim is to provide the missing connection between STEM subjects and real-world interactions and applications, and it is developed with inputs from teachers, researchers, educational experts and industry leaders. The pedagogical foundation is based on problem-based learning, in which active learning is in the centre and learners have to work with different tools and resources in order to solve problems (quests). Teachers facilitate, assess and author pervasive and gamified learning activities (missions). And these quests are gamified in order to provide non-linear game plots. This paper discusses the taxonomy for the Beaconing lesson path, which includes specific categories such as STEM competencies, learning objectives, pedagogical resources, rewards, narratives, game plots, location-based activities and game parameters. The lesson paths developed with the stakeholders will be populated with gamified learning activities such as mini-games, location-based mini-games, location-based activities and physical activities. The lesson paths will scaffold learners through self-directed and independent study, extending the learning experience beyond the classroom settings and complementing existing methods of teaching. The gamified lesson path taxonomy provides the backbone to the Beaconing platform and the associated components. This approach is adoptable and adaptable to various learning objectives.

Keywords: gamified learning activities, gamified lesson path, problem-based learning, STEM education

1. Introduction

21st Century learning focuses on different skills and expertise that learners should develop for a successful life and career, and requires a specific level of knowledge and STEM literacy. This refers to the knowledge and understanding of scientific and mathematical concepts and processes required for personal decision-making, participation in civic and public affairs, and economic productivity for

all learners. Studying STEM or STEM-related subjects will prepare learners to become active citizens and contributors in a science and technology driven world. Different frameworks have been developed to address the skills needed for life and career success, involving a blend of content knowledge, specific skills, expertise and literacies. Binkley et al. (2012) identified ten important skills, divided into four categories: ways of thinking (e.g. creativity and innovation, critical thinking, problem solving, decision making, learning to learn, meta-cognition); ways of working (e.g. communication, collaboration); tools for working (e.g. information literacy, ICT literacy) and living in the world (e.g. citizenship, life and career, personal and social responsibility).

These skills will enable learners to become independent inquirers with a solid understanding of the world and the ability to reason mathematically and critically. The Beaconing approach highlights the need that young people should be encouraged to remain in education and therefore different opportunities should be provided in order for them to enter the higher education and the job market. It recognizes the importance of connecting the teaching and learning process with problem-based mechanics, STEM subjects and these 21st century learning requirements. The Beaconing platform facilitates, assesses and authors contextualised, pervasive and gamified learning activities with the digital activities located in the physical world. Its pedagogical foundation is the problem-based learning, which follows new commercial opportunities and immersive ways of teaching, learning and assessment, and the learners are placed in the centre of the learning process.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the problem-based learning which is the pedagogical foundation of the Beaconing approach. Section 3 presents the methodology of the Beaconing game-based learning design, which focuses on STEM competencies, learning objectives, game mechanics and dynamics. In Section 4 we present the Beaconing taxonomy used by teachers to map, facilitate and assess pervasive and gamified learning activities. Section 5 presents the assessment framework and Section 6 concludes with some remarks on how the Beaconing platform addresses the requirements of the 21st Century learning.

2. Problem-Based Learning

Savin-Baden (2000) defined problem-based learning (PBL) as “an approach to learning that is characterized by flexibility and diversity in the sense that it can be implemented in a variety of ways in and across different subjects and disciplines in diverse contexts. As such it can therefore look very different to different people at different moments in time depending on the staff and students involved in the programs utilize it. However, what will be similar will be the focus of learning around problem scenarios rather than discrete subjects”. In problem-based learning, learners focus on one problem at a time and this problem guides the learning process. The main types of problem-based learning are the pure model and the hybrid model. In pure model the whole curriculum is problem-based and there are no lectures or tutorials, only small teams of learners, while in hybrid model there are some fixed lectures or tutorials only for supporting learners.

The Beaconing approach explores the hybrid problem-based learning approach using a range of blended learning techniques and classroom-based teaching methods. Using the Beaconing platform, learners work in interdisciplinary groups bringing together their scientific inquiry skills, developing a range of employability skills and investigating open-ended real-world problems. The Beaconing’s hybrid approach facilitates active learning, where learners have to work with different tools and resources in order to solve problems (quests). In the Beaconing platform, teachers initiate the problems/quests in the system and learners through self-directed and independent study set their objectives and goals for solving these problems. The problem-based quests can be classroom-based activities, mini-games, location-based mini-games, location-based activities and physical activities.

This approach encourages learners to share and discuss the acquired knowledge and skills with the Beaconing community, and also promotes learners' engagement with learning in general.

3. Methodology

Beaconing employs a holistic approach (see model in Arnab et al. 2015) in mapping the learning needs and context to gamified activities and enabling technologies.

Layer 4: Technology	Interfaces	Media	Analytics	Communication	Content
Layer 3: Game design	Mechanics		Narratives	Aesthetics	UX/EX
Layer 2: Context of learning	Mode	Location	Activities	Assessment	
Layer 1: Learning needs	Learners	Lesson path	Pedagogy	Learning objectives	Measures

Figure 1: A holistic approach for game-based learning considerations (Arnab et al. 2015)

Through this model, the learning needs and contexts inform the types of game-based resources that will be developed. In layer 1, a learner-centric approach has been adopted to put learners at the core of the learning experience, and a lesson path taxonomy has been developed drawing on problem-based learning, as the pedagogical framework. The learning designer focus on learning objectives and the measures that assess student progress. This amplifies their role in the process of content filtering framed under practical, investigative and exploratory scenarios. The Beaconing platform is a source of 'puzzlements' (Wilson, 1996, p. 13) or challenges that are seen as a stimulating learning that is taking place beyond the barriers of space and time, merging formal, non-formal and informal means of learning (layer 2).

Figure 2: Learning path levelling up – a meta-game narrative/story contextualises the missions and quests (Arnab et al. 2015)

Beaconing's focal point is an active learner who interacts with a variety of resources and tools scaffolded by a meta-game approach (layer 3), where narratives play a key role in placing all the learning tasks and activities in context and as a learner's journey. Missions divide the learning path into small iteration cycles that provide scaffolding, and are mapped into game plots, that structure a narrative to engage and situate learning in time and space. Although missions portray the sequential nature adopted by the learning designer, each mission as a number of quests can be explored in a non-linear path and within a multitude of mechanics, providing autonomy to the student (player). Through this, learners develop their own understanding through a mixture of experimentation and guidance. The importance of the collaboration and communication among learners is also

highlighted as part of the learning context, and also the development of learning scenarios that draws on game-based approaches for learning (i.e. the use of a metagame - missions and quests within a narrative, and populated with game-based quests). Figure 2 illustrates the learning path levelling up structure.

The Beaconing platform (layer 4) is also a learning environment where the teachers/learning designers can design learning activities that are underpinned by playful approaches to learning. Through the Beaconing taxonomy, they can map out lesson paths with associated challenges and quests, and link these lesson paths to specific competencies and learning objectives to show learners' progression at specific level. The platform also displays an interface that provides the appropriate tools to integrate teachers and learners in the process, through analytics that measure student's performance, and procedural content generation tools that adapt the contents to each student automatically.

3.1 Learning objectives and STEM Competencies

According to Wagner (2014), the 21st century learner needs seven skills: critical thinking and problem solving; collaboration and leadership; agility and entrepreneurialism; effective oral and written communication; accessing and analysing information; curiosity and imagination. Schools and organizations have adopted and worked toward specific learning objectives for STEM education to bring success and higher school graduation rates.

Beaconing considers STEM competencies, which are informally defined by the Beaconing Consortium as "the set of cognitive knowledge, skills, and abilities that are associated with the STEM disciplines". For the development of the proposed Beaconing taxonomy we focus on the key competencies for STEM (as defined by frameworks, reports, databases, employers, etc.) and the universal competencies both for STEM and non-STEM disciplines.

Jang (2016), through a systematic review on skills and competencies, identified five domains of skills specifically based on STEM disciplines. Jang mapped those skills against a framework developed by Katz and Kahn (1978) and identified five key competencies: problem solving skills (descriptors: critical thinking, complex problem solving, knowledge of mathematics, skills of science, analysing information and creative thinking); social communication skills (descriptors: speaking, coordination, knowledge of customers and personal service, developing and building teams); technology and engineering skills (descriptors: programming, processing information, practical application of disciplinary knowledge); system skills (descriptors: monitoring processes, judging quality, management); and time, resource, knowledge management skills. This review indicates that competencies related to problem solving and social and communication skills are the most common ones, whilst cognitive skills and disciplinary knowledge are also considered essential. All these competencies are included in the Beaconing platform for Beaconing learners to gain the required knowledge and skills beyond STEM.

3.2 Game Mechanics and Dynamics

"Games are a particular manifestation of play, not its totality. They happen to be a good starting point for an investigation of play because the formality of their rules makes the machinery of play easier to observe and analyse" (Upton, 2015). Therefore, games are a means by which play can be observed in a more objective way, leading to purposeful and meaningful engagement and measurement of learning outcomes. In a game situation, the main learning objectives (high-level) can be interpreted and developed through game mechanics (low-level).

The learning and pedagogical requirements should be correlated with game mechanics and dynamics in order to maintain a balance between the entertainment and serious learning objectives.

This approach usually requires an iterative, incremental and user-centric focus (Arnab and Clarke, 2016) that is adopted by Beacons. Dynamics create aesthetic experiences and encourage specific behaviours, skills and abilities, or promote learners' needs, goals and objectives during the gameplay (rules of the mechanics) as "a pattern or process of change, growth, or activity" (Järvinen, 2008).

In the Beacons platform, the game mechanics and dynamics are dependent on the specific learning objectives and pedagogical perspectives of the learning process and activities to support the gamified lesson plans. In Beacons, learning challenges are gamified by being presented in smaller chunks (mini games and classroom activities) to support the constructivism nature of knowledge building in PBL. Mapping out lesson paths with associated learning objectives (e.g. what skills to apply, what knowledge to assess) and challenges defines the content and context of the learning objectives covered in the formal education curriculum. Learning mechanics and dynamics are mapped against the game mechanics and dynamics and guide the learner experience, pervasive engagement and gamified lesson paths.

4. Beacons Taxonomy

The lesson path is the backbone of the Beacons' gamified learning activities. The aim of the Beacons taxonomy (see Figure 3) is to enable gamified lesson paths to be mapped out over a common framework. The proposed taxonomy reflects and focuses on the 21st Century learning requirements, and merges problem-based mechanics and interdisciplinary context with an emphasis on STEM subjects. This taxonomy includes specific categories (e.g. skills/competencies, learning objectives, time frame, evidence, location-based technologies, mini games and so on) that can help end-users to design contextualised and gamified lesson paths for STEM subjects.

What skills participants will develop? Skills/Competencies	What's the purpose? Learning Objectives	How much time? Time	Who is taking part? Players/Participants	Where is the mission going to take place? Places of Interest	What is available for this mission? Tools/Resources	What evidence should participants provide? Evidence	How is achievement rewarded? Rewards/Incentives/Prizes	Location-Based Technologies	Mini Games
Communication/Expression <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advanced literacy Languages Conversation Content creation Self expression Creativity Initiative Mentoring Leadership Reflection Awareness STEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reasoning Inquiry Logical/Spatial Thinking Information skills Social/Civic <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negotiation Assertiveness Respect Integrity Participation Collaboration/team working Adaptability/Resilience Autonomy/Initiative <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning Organisation Management Presentation Entrepreneurship Innovation "Meta" <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning to learn Design thinking Critical/inventive thinking Appreciation Digital literacy Cross-cultural skills 	Science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use science process and thinking skills. Manifest science interests and attitudes. Understand important science concepts and principles. Communicate effectively using science language and reasoning. Demonstrate awareness of the social and historical aspects of science. Understand the nature of science. Technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate an understanding of emerging classroom technologies. Demonstrate knowledge and skills of digital age. Apply technology to facilitate a variety of assessment and evaluation strategies. Understand the social, ethical, and legal issues surrounding technology. Facilitate instruction in the new literacies that emerge within digital interactive learning environments. Engineering <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select and apply appropriate mathematical methods for modeling and analyzing engineering problems. Use scientific principles in the development of engineering solutions to practical problems. Use scientific principles in the modelling and analysis of engineering systems, processes and products Select and apply appropriate computer based methods for modeling and analyzing engineering problems. Mathematics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop fluent knowledge and understanding of mathematical methods. Acquire, select and apply mathematical techniques to solve problems. Reason mathematically and draw conclusions. Comprehend, interpret and communicate mathematical information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> x Hours x Weeks x Months x Sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individuals Small groups Big groups Whole class Whole school Parents Peers Professionals Others 	School <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Classroom Lab ICT room Schoolyard Home <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Friends house Out & About <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Park/Field Museum/Zoo/Science centres/Galleries City centre Shops 	Beacons <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation Online tools/Word processing Online resources (video, newspapers) Models Databases Game apps Beacons Mind-mapping Devices <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobile phones/Laptops/ Camera/Audio Recorder Teachers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lab tools Pen & paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Photographs Tests Quizzes Performance assessments Portfolios Journals Essays Presentations Projects Blog posts Formulas Graphs Charts Computations Peer evaluation Observations Spreadsheets Videos Meeting notes Feedback forms Audio files Demos Prototypes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Points Collectables Peer prestige Vouchers Pass to zoo/aquarium/museum "No homework" pass Badges Certificates Stickers/ribbon/plaque/trophy Educational trips Freebies Customisation options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GPS BLE Beacons Wi-Fi Bluetooth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wack-A-Mole Strategy-builder Puzzle/Reflex Clever-talk Gamified quiz Simulation Game tree Adventure (Treasure hunt)

Figure 3: The Beacons Taxonomy

4.1 Time Allocation

There is a high variability in the educational approaches used in Europe; schools usually have legal and statutory requirements for the time allocated to subjects. Governments determine the time allocation for school programs in the STEM learning areas and subjects, and the Beacons platform supports the recommended curriculum time allocations for the implementation of the gamified

lesson paths. The Beaconsing platform provides gamified lesson paths for learners to effectively acquire the needed knowledge both inside and outside of the classroom. Before teachers plan their lesson paths and allocate the specific time for those, they should identify the specific learning objectives. Then, based on the learning objectives, teachers design appropriate activities with missions and quests that should be accomplished within a certain time period (estimated and specified by teachers).

4.2 Participants

The Beaconsing platform allows teachers to choose whether their students will work individually, in pairs, in small groups or as a whole group. The variation between these options promotes the effectiveness of the gamified activities. When students work on an individual level (e.g. reading, solving problems or case studies), they demonstrate their ideas, views and arguments. Individual activities enable students to work on their own pace and feel comfortable and confident about their knowledge and skills, and to progress through their preferred learning style. Students interact more with each other when they work in pairs or small groups as they can discuss, compare their answers and mark each other's tasks. Working as a whole group is better for review discussions, role-play tasks and formal debates. At group level, learners learn from one another, while the learners' team skills, socialisation and professional networking are improved. Homework is shared and therefore the workload is decreased.

4.3 Places of Interest

The Beaconsing approach recognises in/non formal learning as an extension to formal education, aligning with the hybrid problem-based learning approach towards breaking the barriers of space and time. The gamified learning activities can be undertaken within a formal setting (e.g. classroom, school) and they can be extended to non-formal and informal setting (e.g. co-curricular, local community, home). Learners have both individual and collaborative tasks to solve, from classroom-based activities and after school assignment/homework to workplace internships.

Figure 4: Beaconsing's pervasive schema for the activities (Arnab et al. 2015)

4.4 Tools and Resources

The Beaconsing platform provides various tools and resources to help learners complete their activities. These tools encourage learners to get involved in the gamified activities in an easier and more engaging way. Online tools allow learners to create videos or presentations for the classroom that can be shared among learners. Games and exercises available for computers, mobile devices and tablets also help teachers to easily assess and track learners' progress.

4.5 Evidence

The Beaconing platform has been designed to be flexible towards assessment as there are many particularities and differences in education across Europe; differences in curricula, legal and pedagogical frameworks that drive assessment, levels of education, age and individual needs of learners including those with disabilities. Therefore, it is important that all Beaconing-supported assessment frameworks and practices are flexibly adapted to specific contexts and learners, taking into account the individual, cultural and curricular needs and contexts. Teachers are supported to link the gamified activities (both digital and non-digital) with evidence for specific disciplinary fields, established competence frameworks and well-defined levels of proficiency. The evidence that learners should provide for their assessment are linked with specific weights/measures that are different for each gamified activity as the level of difficulty for each activity is different. These measures are then linked with the assessment framework to assign the learners' level of progress. The Beaconing platform allows learners to upload to the social/discussion platform a variety of evidence formats, such as photos, commentaries, presentations or simple multimedia artefacts (e.g. photographs, blog posts, notes, diaries, spread sheets, videos, demos, prototypes). These evidences are then submitted for peer review and discussion, or for a traditional and formal assessment done by teachers.

4.6 Intrinsic and Extrinsic Incentives and Rewards

During the learning process teachers use different strategies and techniques to encourage and promote appropriate behaviours for positive learning outcomes. In every level of education, learners are usually categorised as intrinsically or extrinsically motivated. Learners who are intrinsically motivated have a desire for learning and in-depth knowledge, whereas extrinsically motivated learners are usually gravitated towards rewards and prizes. Beaconing explores both extrinsic and intrinsic approaches for on boarding learners towards sustained engagement and mastery in specific topics. Intrinsic approach is driven by curiosity and social aspects as well as narratives and stories for engaging learners with the learning journey and missions (in the form of mini-games, etc.). The Beaconing reward system has been designed in such a way to motivate learners by recognising both their effort and performance. Learning and education become more engaging and interactive than the traditional paper-based educational system with the integration of features such as the use of points, badges and leader boards with meaningful and actionable feedback. The analytics component of the platform will synthesise interaction data that will give insights into their learning. Teachers can also award tangible rewards to acknowledge effort, performance and sustained positive behaviour.

4.7 Location-Based Technologies

The Beaconing platform integrates and advances various technologies such as mobile communications, location-based and context-aware systems, and cloud technology. A great emphasis is given on location-based technologies that are widely used in digital games. Location-based games with different play-learn activities are applied to informal learning settings to support problem-based learning. Communication systems and Wi-Fi support the data flow for both indoor and outdoor communications to the platform. When learners are within a specific location, specific sensors (e.g. Beacons in indoor environments or GNSS in outdoor environments) act as a trigger for context-aware systems, and then relevant information with learning resources such as missions and gamified activities is displayed on learners' mobile device.

4.8 Mini-Games

The Beaconing platform exploits pedagogy-driven game techniques such as digital games and gamification to provide an adaptive and personalised digital learning ecosystem. Game-based approaches are extensively used to engage young learners with education and training as they

appeal to all ages and genres. Digital games based on problem-based learning can improve learners' performance, achievements, motivation and satisfaction. Quests provide learning opportunities as challenges, and these challenges can be associated to mini-games. A type of mini game that is included in the Beaconing platform is, the "whack a mole" game (Maynes-Aminzade et al., 2002). This simple type of game invests in long-term memory that can be extracted quickly without conscious effort and can be used for example in Mathematics. The "strategy-builder" games (Selten, 1990) usually support any type of data flow and can challenge learners to build different structures and comprehend the impact of each individual action. "Puzzle" games (Walker and James, 1999) test the learners' problem-solving skills such as logic, pattern recognition, sequence solving and word completion. Puzzle games focus on logical and conceptual challenges, and support intellectual mechanics for comparative intellectual process. "Clever-talk" games (Weibull, 1997) encourage the dialogue and debate between two or more people. "Simulation" games (Ahdoot, 1999) simulate real life situations and are used for various purposes such as training, analysis or learning exercises. With "game trees" (Baxter et al., 1999) learners can explore various learning possibilities and opportunities, while in "adventure" games (Moser, 1997) learners are the protagonists in an interactive story with challenges, exploration and problem solving.

5. Beaconing Assessment Framework

The Beaconing assessment framework allows the learning designer to create a learning path and then gamify it, assuring that, although game plots are non-linear they still allow the learning objectives/competencies to be adequately learned and assessed towards the benchmarks defined. This framework represents the learner's progress and how s/he can move from one challenge to another based on the Triadic Certification approach (Baptista et al., 2015), which is supported by the Triadic Game Design (Harteveld, 2011).

As seen in Figure 5, the learning designer defines the competencies/learning objectives for a specific quest (on the left side of the diagram). And for each one, a set of learning challenges should be gamified (e.g. for S4 a sequence of 4 challenges is defined). Each of these challenges is associated with a specific mini-game that portrays the best opportunity for learning. However these challenges should be also associated with quests that structure the learning progression in discrete game levels, according to a specific game plot. From the bottom right of the diagram the quests are then associated to the challenges to provide progression.

Figure 5: Beaconing Assessment Framework (based on Triadic Certification Approach (Baptista et al., 2015))

Each of the quests provides a non-linear game narrative. The learning designer has a tool that allows the best distribution of these challenges and reveals all paths, assuming distinct possibilities for different students. If a student fails a medium-level challenge, s/he can progress through a distinct

game path with lower difficulty. As seen in figure 6, there are two alternative paths with challenges of distinct difficulties, allowing high-level students to progress faster. But overall the challenges add 100% of the required effort.

Figure 6: Example of an adaptive lesson path

These skills/competencies are obtained when the learner completes a specific quest and achieves a particular score (e.g. completes a quiz, a specific level in a mini game or reading a specific book chapter), and the lesson path given to the learners can automatically adapt to their results (see Figure 7). The level of completion is based on the scores from quizzes, mini games or assessments, the points earned and the time taken for the completion. Each skill/competency has specific weights/measures that are defined by teachers. We number these weights from 0 to 1 (i.e. $0.1 \times s_1 + 0.2 \times s_2 + 0.7 \times s_3$), and they should accumulate to a score of 1 in order to secure a balance between the different skills/competencies. The criteria that determine how these scores are achieved are based on specific measures for each specific skill/competency and quests. Some skills/competencies can be obtained when the learner only completes one quest, whereas others to be obtained, the learner should complete different quests in different challenges. Figure 5 presents a simple example of how the criteria are used in order for a quest to be completed (s_2 is obtained 100% when the learner completes the quest 2 (Q2) in challenge 2 (M2) whereas s_1 is obtained 100% when the learner fully completes quest 1 (Q1), quest 2 (Q2) and quest 3 (Q3) in challenge 1 (M1)). The different levels of quests ensure the learner's progression towards knowledge acquisition and mastery. From Figure 5 the specific weights/measures are missing, as teachers define these weights/measures (each mission/quest has distinct weights/measures).

Figure 7: Example of an adaptive lesson path

6. Conclusions

The main contribution of this paper is to propose a taxonomy that can be used to map out requirements for designing gamified lesson paths based on STEM competencies and learning objectives. The Beacons platform follows a cross subject and problem-based approach with emphasis on contextualised learning within real world problem solving and application. In Beacons platform, the learner is an active contributor who interacts with a variety of resources and tools in order to solve quests or complete missions. The development of the lesson paths draws on gamified learning activities such as mini-games, location-based mini-games, location-based activities and physical activities. The lesson paths scaffold learners through self-directed and independent study, extending the learning experience beyond the classroom settings and complementing existing methods of teaching. The Beacons platform reshapes learning to better match the needs of the

21st century knowledge and open societies, and learners become lifelong learners who are responsible, advanced critical-thinkers, cultural aware, flexible and able to adapt to changes.

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References

- Arnab, S., Tombs, G., Duncan, M., Smith, M., & Star, K. (2015). Towards the Blending of Digital and Physical Learning Contexts with a Gamified and Pervasive Approach. In International Conference on Games and Learning Alliance (pp. 452-460). Springer International Publishing.
- Arnab, S. and Clarke, S. (2016). Towards a trans-disciplinary methodology for a game-based intervention development process. *British Journal of Educational Technology*.
- Ahdoot, N. (1999). Interactive movement and contact simulation game. U.S. Patent 5,913,727.
- Baxter, J., Tridgell, A. and Weaver, L., (1999). Knightcap: a chess program that learns by combining td (λ) with game-tree search. *arXiv preprint cs/9901002*.
- Baptista, R., Nóbrega, R., Coelho, A., Vaz de Carvalho, C. (2015). Location-based tourism in-game certification. *INTED2015 Proceedings*, pp. 3602-3610.
- Binkley, M., Erstad, O., Herman, J., Raizen, S., Ripley, M., Miller-Ricci, M. and Rumble, M. (2012). Defining twenty-first century skills. In *Assessment and teaching of 21st century skills* (pp. 17-66). Springer Netherlands.
- Harteveld, C. (2011). *Triadic game design: Balancing reality, meaning and play*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Jang, H. (2016). Identifying 21st century STEM competencies using workplace data. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 25(2), pp.284-301.
- Järvinen, A. (2008). *Games without frontiers: Theories and methods for game studies and design*. Tampere University Press.
- Katz, D. and Kahn, R.L. (1978). *The social psychology of organizations* (Vol. 2). New York: Wiley.
- Maynes-Aminzade, D., Pausch, R. and Seitz, S. (2002). Techniques for interactive audience participation. In *Proceedings of the 4th IEEE International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces* (p. 15). IEEE Computer Society.
- Moser, R. (1997). A fantasy adventure game as a learning environment: why learning to program is so difficult and what can be done about it. In *ACM SIGCSE Bulletin* (Vol. 29, No. 3, pp. 114-116). ACM.
- Savin-Baden, M. (2000). *Problem-Based Learning In Higher Education: Untold Stories*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Selten, R. (1990). Bounded rationality. *Journal of Institutional and Theoretical Economics (JITE)/Zeitschrift für die gesamte Staatswissenschaft*, 146(4), pp.649-658.
- Upton, B. (2015). *The Aesthetic of Play*. MIT Press.
- Wagner, T. (2014). *The Global Achievement Gap: Updated edition*. Perseus Books Group.
- Walker, J.S. and Jorasch, J. (1999). Electronic word puzzle game. U.S. Patent 5,921,864.
- Weibull, J.W. (1997). *Evolutionary game theory*. MIT press.
- Wilson, B.G. (1996). *Constructivist learning environments: Case studies in instructional design*. Educational Technology.